

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth System**

**Synthesis of Greenland and Antarctic freshwater hosing
experiment**

Milestone MS14

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Milestone report

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1. Means of verification of the achievement of the milestone

This milestone collects information about global climate model simulations done in work packages 5, “Ice sheet impacts on global ocean circulation”, and WP6, “Role of Antarctica in the global climate: Long-term impacts of short-term decision-making” of the OCEAN ICE project. It represents a first step in a cross-model, cross-project synthesis of the impact of ice sheet-derived freshwater fluxes from the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets on the climate. Metrics of the climate context of the simulation (preindustrial control, modern day, future warming), the magnitude of the water fluxes derived from each ice sheet and notes on the apparent impact of the fluxes on the climate are presented. The table in this report itself constitutes the means of verifying the achievement of the milestone.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Introduction

A range of climate simulations with global models have been conducted across WP5 (using NEMO and NorESM2) and WP6 (using UKESM1.2 and PISM-CM2Mc), each looking at different aspects of the role of ice sheets on some aspect of the Earth System

2.1.1 Simulations with NEMO

The NEMO ocean model has been used in standalone mode with a repeating climate forcing, such that the base ocean state represents, as closely as possible, the real ocean state in the 1990s (OI D5.7, de Lavergne and Gülk, 2025). As perturbations to this state, simulations have been run with SO hosing of 0.1Sv matching the SOFIA *antwater* forcing (Swart et al. 2023) and years 1990-2100 of the meltwater projections of OCEAN ICE D4.1 (Coulon et al. 2024). There are also simulations that artificially multiply these hosing fluxes by a factor of 10 (Gülk et al. (preprint)).

2.1.2 Simulations with NorESM2

Simulations in OCEAN ICE with NorESM2 (Goelzer et al. 2025) include an interactive Greenland component providing physically interactive ice sheet freshwater fluxes to the North Atlantic. These may be compared with CMIP6 simulations (Seland et al., 2020), which did not include the Greenland component. In OCEAN ICE, there are simulations under pre-industrial climate conditions with 0.1 Sv of SO hosing following the SOFIA *antwater* and *antwater-60S* protocols (Swart et al 2023), and a climate change scenario following SSP5-8.5 to 2300 (O'Neill et al. 2016) with SO hosing matching freshwater fluxes projected by Coulon et al. (2024). Results from NorESM2 simulations are reported in D5.9.

2.1.3 Simulations with UKESM1.2

UKESM1.2 includes interactive components for both the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets (Smith et al 2024), providing realistic estimates of ice sheet-derived freshwater to the ocean in all simulations. OCEAN ICE MS13 puts the fluxes calculated by UKESM1.2 for Antarctica in the context of the ranges established by OCEAN ICE D4.1 (Coulon et al. 2024). There is a large set of experiments with UKESM1.2 that use an idealised global warming increase with stabilisation at a range of different global warming levels; these are used elsewhere in WP6, and include an experiment where ice shelf basal mass balance is held fixed instead of calculated interactively, providing a "non-hosing" experiment to compare with the interactive case.

In addition to these idealised experiments, there are UKESM1.2 simulations using historical forcings from 1850-2015 and a climate change scenario following SSP5-8.5 to 2100, which are perhaps more directly comparable to the other model scenarios synthesised in this MS.

2.1.4 Simulations with PISM-CM2Mc

The CM2Mc global climate model has been coupled to an Antarctic ice sheet component (Kreuzer et al., 2021) and used to run simulations in OCEAN ICE. Simulations have been conducted using just the climate component, CM2Mc, under pre-industrial control conditions and a climate change scenario using an idealised 1% increase in the concentration of atmospheric carbon dioxide with a SO hosing flux of regionally varying Antarctic melt and calving fluxes along the coastline provided from a PISM spinup (Kreuzer et al., 2026).

2.2 Synthesis table

Model	Climate Scenario	Length of run	Ant FWF	GrIS FWF	AMOC	SO deepwater formation
UKESM1.2	Idealised warming at 2K/century	~300 years	prognostic. slowly increases, at the lower end of Coulon' 24 envelope for all components	prognostic. steadily increasing from ~400 -> 1500Gt/yr. (Max ~0.05Sv)	strength at 26N: steadily declines from 14->6Sv	(result not available)
UKESM1.2	piControl	~150 years	prognostic. steady, at the lower end of Coulon's 24 envelope for BMB and iceberg melt, surface runoff is small but non-negligible above estimates	prognostic. steady at ~400 Gt/yr (0.01Sv)	strength at 26N: steady around 14 +/- 1Sv	Minimum value below 55S: steady around -24Sv
UKESM1.2	Historical	165 years	BMB+iceberg melt+ surface runoff fluctuate around 3000 Gt/yr before 1950 and start to decrease to 2000 Gt/yr by 2014	BMB+iceberg melt+ surface runoff fluctuate around 900 Gt/yr without an obvious trend	Strength at 26N: steady at ~17Sv	Minimum value below 55S: fluctuates between -20Sv and -32Sv
UKESM1.2	SSP5-8.5	85 years	BMB+iceberg melt+ surface runoff increase from	BMB+iceberg melt+ surface runoff	strength at 26N: Declines from 16->11Sv by	Minimum value below 55S: declines

Model	Climate Scenario	Length of run	Ant FWF	GrIS FWF	AMOC	SO deepwater formation
			~3000->8000Gt/yr by 2099	increase from ~900->3000 Gt/yr by 2099	2099	from about -28->-17.5 Sv by 2099
UKESM1.2	Extended SSP5-8.5	185 years	BMB+iceberg melt+ surface runoff increase from ~3000->16000Gt/yr by 2199	BMB+iceberg melt+ surface runoff increase from ~600->8500Gt/yr by 2099	strength at 26N:Declines from 14.5->8.5Sv by 2199	Minimum value below 55S: declines from about -18->-2 Sv by 2199
PISM-CM2Mc	Idealized warming with 1% CO2 increase in the first 140 years, const. after	740 years	Up to 1500 Gt/yr (0.05 Sv) additional discharge from AIS	only varying via river runoff with precipitation change	declines 20->16Sv for warming (Increases slightly if only FW added)	Reduces 19->13 Sv, with shallower mixed layer depth
NorESM2	piControl	200 years	SOFIA antwater (0.1 Sv)	Prognostic	No significant response	Lower cell weakens by ~50%
NorESM2	piControl	130 years (so far)	SOFIA antwater-60s	Prognostic	No significant response	Lower cell weakens by ~25%
NorESM2	SSP5-8.5	285 years	No additional FW	Prognostic	Weakens from ~20 to 8 Sv by 2150	Lower cell weakens by ~50%
NorESM2	SSP5-8.5	285 years	Coulon et al. 2024 FW	Prognostic	Follows SSP5-8.5 without added FW	Follows SSP5-8.5 without added FW
NorESM2	SSP5-8.5	200 years	Coulon et al. 2024 FW (40 years earlier)	Prognostic	Follows SSP5-8.5 without added FW	Follows SSP5-8.5 without added FW
NEMO	Climatological repeat-year	111 years	SOFIA-antwater (0.1 Sv)	Climatological as river runoff	Increases from 1990 - ~2070 from 17Sv to 19Sv, then decreases to 17.5Sv	At 64°S: Declines quickly from 16Sv to ~4 Sv

Model	Climate Scenario	Length of run	Ant FWF	GrIS FWF	AMOC	SO deepwater formation
NEMO	Climatological repeat-year	111 years	Coulon et al. 2024 FW (surface)	Climatological as river runoff	Increases from 1990 - 2100 from 17Sv to 19Sv	Declines constantly from 16Sv to ~5 Sv
NEMO	Climatological repeat-year	111 years	Coulon et al. 2024 FW (3D distribution)	Climatological as river runoff	Follows Coulon (surface)	Declines slowly from 16Sv to ~10 Sv
NEMO	Climatological repeat-year	111 years	10x SOFIA-antwater (1 Sv)	Climatological as river runoff	Increases from 1990 - ~2040 from 17Sv to 19Sv, then decreases to 8Sv	Follows SOFIA-antwater
NEMO	Climatological repeat-year	111 years	10x Coulon et al. 2024 FW (surface)	Climatological as river runoff	Increases from 1990 - ~2070 from 17Sv to 19Sv, then decreases to 18Sv	Follows SOFIA-antwater
NEMO	Climatological repeat-year	111 years	10x Coulon et al. 2024 FW (3D distribution)	Climatological as river runoff	Follows 10xCoulon (surface)	Declines after ~2050 to ~4 Sv

2.3 References

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2.4 Open Science

Further analysis of the simulations noted in this report will form part of the final OCEAN ICE deliverable report from the cross-cutting theme "The Role of the Poles" and, if published in the peer-reviewed literature, will be freely available in an open repository along with the datasets used in the analysis.

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